

Urban access is inequitably distributed in cities across the world

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Summary

Disparity in spatial accessibility manifests as an outcome of and is responsible for growing poverty among urban communities. Since improving levels of accessibility can address social exclusion and poverty, it is important to understand the nature and distribution of spatial accessibility among urban communities. To support decision-makers in achieving inclusion and fairness in policy interventions in cities, we present an open-source and data-driven framework to understand the spatial nature of accessibility to infrastructure among the different demographics in cities. We find systematically low accessibility scores for populations who have a larger share of minorities, earn less, and have a relatively lower number of individuals with a university degree. These findings suggest that such an approach can support cities to devise targeted measures for addressing inequalities for certain underprivileged communities.

KEYWORDS: urban accessibility, equity, public policy, open source data, machine learning

1. Introduction

While national and regional level policies around globalisation, migration and free-market investments have catapulted urban economies, the benefits have not accrued equitably across urban populations (Nijman and Wei 2020). Multiple *de-jure* and *de-facto* urban processes (gentrification, segregation, exclusionary zoning laws) (Parekh and Gaztambide-Fernández 2017) have pushed low-income minority groups to live in deteriorated urban areas receiving a minor share of public investments (Rothstein 2015; Rothstein 2017), resulting in strong inequalities among urban residents around the world (Sydes 2019; Bayón and Saraví 2018).

Many of the inequalities that exist in cities have a strong spatial context (Nijman and Wei 2020) rooted in access to infrastructure. Depending on their socio-economic status (McFarlane and Rutherford 2008), people living in areas with a poor concentration of accessible services and amenities

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(Mayaud, Tran, and Nuttall 2019) tend to snowball into low levels of education, poor physical and mental health, disproportionate job opportunities and social exclusion (Massey, Condran, and Denton 1987; Gobillon and Selod 2007; Glaeser, Resseger, and Tobio 2009; Rothstein 2017), thus lacking any upward mobility.

Accessibility refers to the ease with which residents within a city can reach amenities or opportunities (destinations, social interactions, jobs) (Levinson and King 2020; Hewko, Smoyer-Tomic, and Hodgson 2002; Biazzo, Monechi, and Loreto 2019) by walking or by using a form of *active* transportation (e.g. bicycle or roller-blades) (Vale, Saraiva, and M. Pereira 2016). Active accessibility plays a central role within accessibility policy worldwide (Seskin and McCann 2012; Vale, Saraiva, and M. Pereira 2016) and is used as a measure to quantify urban livability for decision-making (Orozco et al. 2019). It is a measure adopted by planners to understand how land-use and transport systems shape the quality of life of residents in a city and identify where equitable developments can improve the lives of marginalised communities (Levinson and King 2020). Akin to the notion that to survive a decline, cities must provide attractive amenities for increasingly rich workers (Glaeser, Kolko, and Saiz 2001), the responsibility of equitably addressing urban inequalities also lies with municipal authorities (Seskin and McCann 2012).

Through sociological investigations and observations, scholars have illustrated how interlinked social factors are related to urban inequalities across spatial and temporal scales (Nijman and Wei 2020). Also, literature focusing on urban inequalities through the availability of open-source data, highlights only specific aspects of accessibility, such as transit, health or green space infrastructure, and (in-)equalities by specific social attributes, such as income or ethnicity (Jang et al. 2017; Mayaud, Tran, and Nuttall 2019; Xiao et al. 2017). However, to focus on equitable urban planning, we need to understand the fundamental nature of accessibility and inequalities related to it. Our research presents a data-driven framework to evaluate the differences in access to urban infrastructure afforded by different demographics within cities around the world. We find that accessibility in all cities is driven by a simple universal law, despite the geographical, historical, cultural, and political differences that exist across these cities. By taking into consideration several categories of socio-economic attributes of urban populations, we assess the inequitable distribution of accessibility. Our findings reveal the existence of systemic socio-economic inequalities across North American cities. The modular framework we have developed can be used to identify urban areas for interventions in addressing urban inequalities by municipalities around the world.

2. Methodology

2.1. Framework

To identify the nature of inequalities that citizens face in access to urban infrastructure worldwide, we introduce a framework that facilitates comparison of accessibility scores of groups of households that share similar socio-economic attributes (e.g. income, employment, mobility) within and across cities. By leveraging open-source data about urban form and socio-economic information, we conduct this study for 54 cities across six continents. We measure accessibility for all 54 cities and examine the variability in its distribution for the city population on a subset of those cities: New York City, Chicago, San Francisco, Los Angeles, Houston, Seattle, Miami, Toronto, Vancouver, and Montreal. Within this subset, the municipal authorities of each city have made strong policy efforts

to provide equitable access to urban services within their municipal jurisdiction (Seskin and McCann 2012). Besides, open-source data programs run by the municipal governments of these cities provide aggregated socio-economic variables for the complete population.

2.2. Accessibility

To compute accessibility, we use amenities’ data from OpenStreetMap. To reflect on broader attributes of functional and livable urban spaces: transportation, public health, food security, cultural capital, and social cohesion (Kenworthy 2006; Leby and Hashim 2010), we classify each point of interest into one of *seven* categories of accessibility: Mobility, Active living, Entertainment, Food Choices, Community Space, Education, Health and Well Being. For each spatial unit (hexagons¹) in a city, we calculate the average routing distance (Xu et al. 2020) (Euclidean distances do not take into account land-use and urban form (Gastner and Newman 2006)) a resident would travel from a node to an amenity (that may or may not be in the same hexagon). Thus, we compute the average walking distance within every hexagon of a city to each of the seven categories of basic amenities. Next, we weigh and aggregate average walking distances into a walking distance measure D using the following equation:

$$D_i = \log\left(\sum_c w^c d_i^c\right), \quad (1)$$

where d is the average walking distance of nodes that fall within hexagon i to the nearest amenity of a given category c , and w (constant across all cities and hexagons) is the weight attributed to that category. The use of a logarithmic function captures the outliers in the measurement and makes comparison easier within and across cities. Finally, we measure the accessibility score A as follows,

$$A_i = 1 - \widetilde{D}_i, \quad (2)$$

where large values of A_i indicate high accessibility and low values indicate low accessibility (\widetilde{D}_i is obtained by normalizing D_i using a min-max scaler function). We normalize the measure within each city so we can normatively rank walking distances of every hexagon relative to each city and compare the distributions across cities.

3. Results

3.1. The Law of accessibility

Regardless of the history of each city, accessibility in a city follows a universal log-normal distribution (Figure 1). The level of access in any spatial unit is inversely proportional to its rank in the accessibility score. A scale-free law (Gabaix 1999) governing the cumulative distribution of accessibility across the world could be explained by the concentration of populations in growing urban

¹Spatial units are equally-sized 0.45 km² hexagonal grids to reduce sampling bias from edge effects (Mayaud, Tran, R. H. Pereira, et al. 2019) and address the Modifiable Areal Unit Problem (MAUP) (Dark and Bram 2007).

Figure 1(A) The probability density functions of accessibility for the ten subset cities. Each curve represents the statistical distribution of hexagons based on their accessibility score, within a given city. The coloured dots represent equal-sized hexagons within each city with yellow being most accessible and black, the least.

regions that are economically well-integrated (Cristelli, Batty, and Pietronero 2012). While from the supply side, the distribution of access to amenities shows that many areas have low levels of access, those areas also have a higher density of populations, thus indicating a need to address the disparity in access, even in cities whose density distributions are left-skewed.

As Zipf’s formulation above suggests, certain regions in a city suffer from low access. To understand the composition of communities that have lower access, we examine the relationship between accessibility and the socio-economic attributes of households within the spatial units in a city using the city of Chicago as an example representation. We selected socio-economic attributes that were largely available in the census data across Canada and the United States of America (USA). Using the method of consensus clustering (Monti et al. 2003) on socio-economic variables, we identified *five* urban profiles for each city in our original subset:

- Low income mixed (LIMix)
- Low income minority (LIMin)
- Medium income white (MIW)
- High income white (HIW)
- Medium income white (MIW)

Figure 2(A) Spatial representation of the five clustered social groups for Chicago. (B) The spatial distribution of accessibility for Chicago, where each spatial unit (an equal-sized hexagon of 0.45 km²) has its own accessibility score. (C) A box-plot showing the variability in access for each of Chicago’s clustered social groups. (D) Kernel density estimations of normalized demographic attributes that are prevalent for each of Chicago’s clustered social groups.

Figure 2A-B visually depicts the spatial differences in accessibility for each urban profile in Chicago, largely indicating that the highest accessibility is concentrated in areas characterised by the HIW urban profile. Observe in Figure 2C-F that, the prevalent socio-economic features of the profile with least levels of access are characterised by the lowest levels of income, the highest ratio of individuals who identify as visible minorities, the lowest number of individuals with a university education, and the highest rates of unemployment. On average, urban areas inhabited by the most disadvantaged group in Chicago are 13% less accessible than those inhabited by the least disadvantaged group. If we break down accessibility by category in Chicago, the highest degrees of inequality are found in access to infrastructure related to food choices, entertainment, active living, and health and well-being. The rest of the cities exhibit a similar pattern where social groups with the least levels of access (sans HIW groups in some cities that live in rich suburban communities) also suffer from low levels of education, unemployment and low income and have a higher proportion of minority groups.

4. Conclusions and Discussion

Urban planning varies in practice across cities around the world, with diverse values embedded in providing public infrastructures, coupled with bottom-up processes of change within neighbourhoods. In spite of this, spatial distribution of access follows a universal log-normal paradigm, indicating a bimodal distribution of population (one with increasingly high access, and another with lower levels of access). In accordance with Zipf's laws of cities (Gabaix 1999), but also considering the economic integration of urban regions (Cristelli, Batty, and Pietronero 2012), some cities exhibit a widening inequality across spatial lines. Our findings suggest that the distribution of amenities in cities plays a significant role in addressing inequalities in access to urban infrastructure. The most socio-economically disadvantaged groups are systemically underserved by urban infrastructure as compared to least disadvantaged groups. When aggregated by category of accessibility, there is a gap in access to food, culture and entertainment, active living and health infrastructure, which is all more accessible in spatial units where the least vulnerable profiles reside. Our research provides a holistic and reproducible framework for municipalities worldwide to incorporate equitable decision making based on improved access to infrastructure for all.

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References

- Bayón, María Cristina and Gonzalo A Saraví (2018). "Place, Class interaction, and urban Segregation: experiencing inequality in México City". In: *Space and Culture* 21.3, pp. 291–305.
- Biazzo, Indaco, Bernardo Monechi, and Vittorio Loreto (2019). "General scores for accessibility and inequality measures in urban areas". In: *Royal Society open science* 6.8, p. 190979.
- Cristelli, Matthieu, Michael Batty, and Luciano Pietronero (2012). "There is more than a power law in Zipf". In: *Scientific reports* 2, p. 812.
- Dark, Shawna J and Danielle Bram (2007). "The modifiable areal unit problem (MAUP) in physical geography". In: *Progress in Physical Geography* 31.5, pp. 471–479.
- Gabaix, Xavier (1999). "Zipf's law for cities: an explanation". In: *The Quarterly journal of economics* 114.3, pp. 739–767.
- Gastner, Michael T and Mark EJ Newman (2006). "Optimal design of spatial distribution networks". In: *Physical Review E* 74.1, p. 016117.
- Glaeser, Edward L, Jed Kolko, and Albert Saiz (2001). "Consumer city". In: *Journal of economic geography* 1.1, pp. 27–50.
- Glaeser, Edward L, Matt Resseger, and Kristina Tobio (2009). "Inequality in cities". In: *Journal of Regional Science* 49.4, pp. 617–646.
- Gobillon, Laurent and Harris Selod (2007). "The effect of segregation and spatial mismatch on unemployment: evidence from France". In.

- Hewko, Jared, Karen E Smoyer-Tomic, and M John Hodgson (2002). “Measuring neighbourhood spatial accessibility to urban amenities: does aggregation error matter?” In: *Environment and Planning A* 34.7, pp. 1185–1206.
- Jang, Seongman et al. (2017). “Assessing the spatial equity of Seoul’s public transportation using the Gini coefficient based on its accessibility”. In: *International Journal of Urban Sciences* 21.1, pp. 91–107.
- Kenworthy, Jeffrey R (2006). “The eco-city: ten key transport and planning dimensions for sustainable city development”. In: *Environment and urbanization* 18.1, pp. 67–85.
- Leby, Jasmine Lau and Ahmad Hariza Hashim (2010). “Liveability dimensions and attributes: Their relative importance in the eyes of neighbourhood residents”. In: *Journal of construction in developing countries* 15.1, pp. 67–91.
- Levinson, David and David King (2020). “Transport Access Manual: A Guide for Measuring Connection between People and Places”. In.
- Massey, Douglas S, Gretchen A Condran, and Nancy A Denton (1987). “The effect of residential segregation on black social and economic well-being”. In: *Social Forces* 66.1, pp. 29–56.
- Mayaud, Jerome R, Martino Tran, and Rohan Nuttall (2019). “An urban data framework for assessing equity in cities: Comparing accessibility to healthcare facilities in Cascadia”. In: *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems* 78, p. 101401.
- Mayaud, Jerome R, Martino Tran, Rafael HM Pereira, et al. (2019). “Future access to essential services in a growing smart city: The case of Surrey, British Columbia”. In: *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems* 73, pp. 1–15.
- McFarlane, Colin and Jonathan Rutherford (2008). “Political infrastructures: Governing and experiencing the fabric of the city”. In: *International journal of urban and regional research* 32.2, pp. 363–374.
- Monti, Stefano et al. (2003). “Consensus clustering: a resampling-based method for class discovery and visualization of gene expression microarray data”. In: *Machine learning* 52.1-2, pp. 91–118.
- Nijman, Jan and Yehua Dennis Wei (2020). “Urban inequalities in the 21st century economy”. In: *Applied Geography*, p. 102188.
- Orozco, Luis Guillermo Natera et al. (2019). “Quantifying Life Quality as Walkability on Urban Networks: The Case of Budapest”. In: *International Conference on Complex Networks and Their Applications*. Springer, pp. 905–918.
- Parekh, Gillian and Rubén Gaztambide-Fernández (2017). “The more things change: Durable inequalities and new forms of segregation in Canadian public schools”. In: *Second international handbook of urban education*. Springer, pp. 809–831.
- Rothstein, Richard (2015). “The racial achievement gap, segregated schools, and segregated neighborhoods: A constitutional insult”. In: *Race and social problems* 7.1, pp. 21–30.
- (2017). *The color of law: A forgotten history of how our government segregated America*. Liveright Publishing.
- Seskin, Stefanie and Barbara McCann (2012). “Complete streets policy analysis 2011”. In.
- Sydes, Michelle (2019). “Where immigrants live: capturing ethnic segregation at the local level in two Australian cities”. In: *Australian Geographer* 50.2, pp. 221–241.
- Vale, David S, Miguel Saraiva, and Mauro Pereira (2016). “Active accessibility: A review of operational measures of walking and cycling accessibility”. In: *Journal of transport and land use* 9.1, pp. 209–235.
- Xiao, Yang et al. (2017). “An assessment of urban park access in Shanghai—Implications for the social equity in urban China”. In: *Landscape and urban planning* 157, pp. 383–393.
- Xu, Yanyan et al. (2020). “Deconstructing laws of accessibility and facility distribution in cities”. In: *Science advances* 6.37, eabb4112.

Biographies

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